

GLOBAL CONSTANTS

```
const double  q=1.6e-19    ///[kl] particle charge
              ,m=25.6e-27 ///[kg] particle mass
              ,theta=1
              ,T=10e4      ///[K] temperature
              ,B0=20       ///[nT] initial magnetic field
              ,E0=1e3*q/theta ///[eV] energy
              ,v0=sqrt(2*E0/m)
```

GRID CONSTANTS

```
const double  Pho_v= (m)/(q*B0*1e-9)
double  x0=x0, y0=y0, z0=y0, vx0=vx0, vy0=vy0,vz0=vy0;
```

```
const double  delta=1
              ,tau0= delta*Pho_v
              ,Theta_m=1.      ///mass ratio of O+ and O+-O+8
              ,Theta_q=1.     ///charge ratio of O+ and O+-O+8
              ,theta_2=Theta_q/Theta_m*delta;
double  Lz=Lz, Lx=Lx, Ly=Ly;
```

//-----

In the given magnetic and electric fields, the integration of particle motion equations was carried out:

```
int FCN (int  N, double  t, double * x , double * DERY)
{
double  bx=bx , by=by, bz=bz;
double  Ex= Ex, Ey= Ey, Ez= Ez;
}
DERY [0] = x [3] ;
DERY [1] = x [4] ;
DERY [2] = x [5] ;
DERY [3] = theta_2*(Ex + 1*(bz*x[4]-by*x[5]));
DERY [4] = theta_2*(Ey + 1*(bx*x[5]-bz*x[3]));
DERY [5] = theta_2*(Ez + 1*(by*x[3]-bx*x[4]));
return 0 ;
}
```

```
int OUTY (double  t, double * x, FILE  * pfp)
{
double  bx=bx , by=by, bz=bz;
double  Ex= Ex, Ey= Ey, Ez= Ez;
}
{
fprintf ( pfp , "%8.3g %8.4g %10.4g \n"
        , t, x[0], x[1], x[2],x[3], x[4], x[5], bx, by, bz, Ex, Ey, Ez) ;
return 0 ;
}
}
```

Set the initial distribution function:

```
double Kappa(){
double k,n_0,A_ke, E_0, ED , Ek=E_0*(2-3./k) , T=1;
double step=0.0005;
double f ;
double y = double(rand())/RAND_MAX;
double s = 0., lgE = log10(1.);
while (s < y){
lgE=lgE+step;
f=n_0*A_ke*pow(pi*k*Ek,-3/2)*(pow(1+(1/T)*(pow(10,lgE)+ED-2*sqrt(ED*pow(10,lgE)/3)))/k*Ek,-
(k+1))+pow(1+(1/T)*(pow(10,lgE)+ED+2*sqrt(ED*pow(10,lgE)/3)))/k*Ek,-(k+1));
s=s+f*step;
}
return sqrt(pow(10,lgE));
}
```

```

int main()
{

double* x= new double [6];
double* x_new= new double [6];
double dt;
double v =Kappa();
x[0] = x0;
x[1] = y0;
x[2] = z0;
x[3] =vx0;
x[4] =vy0;
x[5] =vz0;
dt=t1/v*Pho_v;
.....
FILE * pfp ;
pfp = fopen ( "File.txt" , "w" ); if ( pfp == NULL ) return 0 ;
t =0;
for ( iStep = 0; iStep <= NSTEPS; iStep++ )
{
tEND1 = iStep *dt;
dverk (..);
if (x[0] < -Lx || x[0] > Lx ) break;
if (x[1] < -Ly || x[1] > Ly ) break;
if (x[2] < -Lz || x[2] > Lz )break;
if ( iStep == 0 ||iStep == NSTEPS ||iStep % 1 == 0);
OUTY( t ,x,pfp)

} fclose ( pfp) ;
delete [] x;
delete [] x_new;
return 1 ;
}

```